

Effective telescoping single solvent continuous-flow synthesis of Rivaroxaban in a micro-reactor

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ABSTRACT—

This paper focus on the micro reactor driven single solvent telescoped process for desire Rivaroxaban API synthesis. Over here flow chemistry was used to construct heterocyclic ring, which is the basic building block of the molecule. In this synthesis method, traditional batch pathway was isolated and reactions were conducted by using flow micro reactors. Isolated final compound was analyzed by using spectral studies such that ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR.

KEYWORDS - Flow chemistry, API, Multistep synthesis, Flow synthesis, Micro-reactor

INTRODUCTION –

Over the last decade, there had been a significant increase in flow chemistry publications, presentations, and lectures. Initially, this field was dominated by chemical engineers only, but now a days it become a need in research and development in drug discovery, drug development and manufacturing, that's why both chemists and chemical engineers are working together for the growth of flow chemistry. Main target of their combined efforts are to achieve outcomes that would be beyond the reach or not practical by using conventional batch equipment.¹ As it expand the range of chemical transformations available for the synthesis of new compound, the demand of flow chemistry among synthetic chemists is remarkable. Many publications in this field have been documented in scholarly articles journal ² which specifies importance of this new technique in the manufacturing of chemical entities.

Flow chemistry has one of the features known as Microreactor.³⁻⁴

What is Micro reactor?

Micro fluidic reactors, which work on a tiny scale, benefit from the special properties of fluid flow at this level. They are most effective when their size is less than 500 μm , which is often considered the limit for a micro fluidic reactor. However, a more flexible view includes reactors that work at low Reynolds and thermal Péclet numbers, below 250 and 1,000, respectively. This means that reactors with sizes between 500 and 1,000 μm can also be considered micro fluidic, depending on the flow rate. These reactors fall into a category called 'mesofluidic,' which ranges from 500 to a few mm. It's important to note that as the size of the reactor gets bigger than 1 mm, it becomes hard to keep the fluid flow in the micro scale.

Micro reactors are usually operated continuously. This allows the further processing of unstable intermediates, by avoiding usual batch workup delays. Temperature dependant chemistry with less reaction time is no longer held for hours until reagent dosing is completed and the next reaction step can be conducted. This quick work-up minimizes degradation and frequently allows greater selectivity.

Micro reactors have heat exchange coefficients of up to 500 $\text{MW m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$, compared to a few kilowatts in conventional glassware (1 L flask $\sim 10 \text{ kW m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$). As a result, micro reactors can drag heat much more efficiently than vessels, and even critical reactions like nitrations can be performed safely at elevated temperatures. ⁵ Exothermicity considerably reduces the hot spot temperature generation and high temperature duration exposition. Micro reactors allow more accurate reaction kinetic studies, because local temperature gradients which directly affects reaction rate are much smaller in micro reactor as compared to any of the traditional batch reactor. These can be heated and cooled quickly, with operating temperatures as low as -100°C .

Reynolds number:

The Reynolds number (Re) is a dimensionless number used to quantify the relative importance of inertial and viscous forces within a fluid:

$$\text{Re} = (\text{inertial forces})/(\text{viscous forces}) = \rho d v / \mu$$

Here, ρ is density,

μ is dynamic viscosity,

v is fluid velocity,

d is characteristic dimension.

The Reynolds number accounts for characteristics of both the fluid (density, ρ , and dynamic viscosity, μ) and the environment in which the fluid is manipulated (fluid velocity, v , and characteristic dimension, d). Fluid flow in micro fluidic devices is characterized by low Reynolds numbers (generally below 250) and is located in the laminar flow regime. When chemical reactions are performed in micro fluidic reactors, low Reynolds number ensures that there is no turbulence and hence no back-mixing within the reactor.

Thermal Péclet number:

The thermal Péclet number (PeL) is a dimensionless number often used to characterize the micro fluidic regime. It describes the ratio between heat transport due to advective and diffusive transport, that is:

$$PeL = \text{advective/diffusive} = d v \rho C_p / k$$

Here, d is the channel diameter,

v is the fluid velocity,

ρ is the density of the fluid,

k is the thermal conductivity of the fluid and

C_p is its specific heat capacity

The thermal Péclet number is specially relevant for chemistry in a micro fluidic environment as it describes the relative importance of heat transfer due to bulk fluid motion and conductive heat transfer. For example, in a micro fluidic channel where heat is applied to the channel wall, the thermal Péclet number will define how rapidly heat is carried by the moving fluid relative to how fast it is transferred from the channel wall to the center of the fluid flow.

When compared to traditional batch processes, continuous operation and mixing gives a completely distinct concentration profile. In a batch, reagent A is filled and reagent B is slowly added. Thus, B initially encounters a large excess of A. In a micro reactor, A and B both meet and combined rapidly, and B is not exposed to an excessive amount of A. Over here Reynolds number and thermal Péclet number really plays an important role. Reynolds number describes mixing extend and thermal Péclet number will explain utility drag.

This new technology offers several benefits, like

- Due to its large surface area and small heat capacity, it allows for precise temperature control
- The time it takes for a reaction to occur can be easily adjusted by changing the flow rate and size of the reactor
- The equipment needed is small, and the mixing of reactants is quick
- Surface to volume ratio ⁶⁻⁷ in the system is high, which is good for reactions
- It also makes it possible to perform reactions efficiently using laminar or slug flow
- This also reduces the formation of unwanted by-products and minimizes waste from solvents and reagents, making the process environmentally friendly.

Due to these reasons micro flow reactors are becoming a popular alternative to traditional batch reactors for various types of reactions.

By combining this technique with telescoping method, we have synthesized Rivaroxaban. Rivaroxaban is used to treat Deep Vein Thrombosis⁸ (DVT; a blood clot, usually in the leg) and Pulmonary Embolism⁹ (PE; a blood clot in the lung) in adults. In addition, it is used to prevent PE and DVT in adult patients undergoing knee or hip replacement surgery, as well as in patients hospitalized for severe illnesses that run the risk of clotting because of reduced

mobility or additional risk factors. It is also used in conjunction with aspirin¹⁰ to reduce the risk of a heart attack, stroke, or death. In children and some newborns that have had at least five days of initial anticoagulation (blood thinner) medication, Rivaroxaban is also used to treat and prevent DVT and PE from reoccurring.

One of the beautification of flow chemistry is that, multistep reactions can be arranged sequentially without isolation of intermediates, if they are unstable, air sensitive or poisonous. By taking this in to account, here we have successfully synthesized Rivaroxaban with the help of telescoped micro flow reactor. In this entire course of reaction four micro reactors were used in which five chemical transformations were incorporated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Chemistry: In this paper Rivaroxaban API (Scheme -1) was synthesized with the help of flow chemistry (Figure -1). Over here the main interesting part was synthesis of Oxazolidone ring (Inter -3) by treating (Inter-1) and CDI. This reaction specially shows heterocyclic ring construction with the help of flow chemistry.

General Information: In this paper we had synthesized, Rivaroxaban by telescoping multi-step process with micro-flow reactor by using a single solvent. These features motivated us to improve flow methodology for synthesis application. We had followed following systematic steps to land up robust, very simple and easy to automate telescoping process for Rivaroxaban synthesis.

At first, we had literature survey and try to find out the solvents used in each step. It was observed that for a separate step separate solvent was used. We checked solubility and solvent compatibility of the starting material, intermediates and reagents. After careful examination; we selected DMSO, DMF, DMAc as a solvent for reaction. We put individual batch reaction with theses solvents and observed good yield and quality when DMSO was used.

In this multistep synthesis, we had recommended that every time one step is optimized, we would execute it on a big scale (100g) and isolate the final Rivaroxaban API using a conventional method to evaluate the efficiency of flow step.

Initially reaction conducted between Amine and Oxirane with extreme dilution (0.05M each solution) to avoid chocking. After completion of the reaction we reduced solvent contribution and finally landed up to 1.5M Amine and 0.85M Oxirane. Here temperature and residence time behavior was studied and concluded that reaction complies well in 46Sec at 60°C.

For second step CDI solubility was a crucial point. During study, it was observed that when less DMSO was used, after some time CDI solid get precipitates and when more DMSO get used, due to dilution factor, reaction takes more time to comply. Hence in-between 2.2M CDI in DMSO this ration was freeze for reaction. In this condition reaction temperature range was

studied and concluded 60°C a better point for reaction. Multiple reactions with above freeze parameters landed up the best conversion at 36 Sec residence time.

For third step, we have used DMSO in which MMA gas was dissolved. This activity was done separately in round bottom flask and MMA gas purged in DMSO at 0-5°C. Sufficient concentration of MMA easily identified and calculated by periodic DMSO reaction mass weight check. When it reaches to 2.5M, it became ready to use and Peristaltic pump was used to feed this MMA solution. From now onwards we kept reaction temperature fix 60°C only and varies the residence time. Best reaction conversion was observed at 55 Sec residence time.

For fourth step Chloro thio compound was diluted in DMSO. Over here main concern was to fix the molarity of this reagent. Initially when we did this reaction with neat Chloro thio compound, the reactor got choked due to precipitation of MMA-HCl salt. After careful examination of the precipitated salt, we conclude that whatever MMA-HCl salt is precipitating, it has to dissolve in the reaction solvent. Hence we had increased DMSO concentration slowly and landed up to 3M Chloro-thio compound in DMSO. This molarity was sufficient to drive the reaction in forward direction without reactor choking. As mentioned earlier reaction temperature was fixed at 60°C and reaction complies in minimum 43 sec.

EXPERIMENTAL:

Chemicals of laboratory quality were procured from S.D. Fine Chemicals (Mumbai, India) for the synthesis. The melting point was determined using open capillary tubes in a Hicon, India apparatus, and the results were left uncorrected. Every reaction progress was regularly observed via thin-layer chromatography (TLC) with Merck silica gel 60 F254 coated aluminum plates and a variety of solvent systems with varying polarities like Ethyl acetate: Hexane, Methanol : Dichloromethane and Methanol : Ethyl acetate in various percentage combinations were used as mobile phases. By using a TMS internal reference standard (chemical shifts in δ), ¹H NMR (400 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz) were recorded on DMSO-d₆ solution in a 5 mm tube on a Varian 400 MHz Unity Inova.

Reported reaction scheme for preparation of Rivaroxaban patent WO2015/198259 A1 (Example 1, 2 and 3)

[SCHEME – 1]

SCHEME – 1: SYNTHESIS OF RIVAROXABAN

The synthesis of Rivaroxaban discussed in the patent WO2015/198259 A1 with reference to above scheme, step wise process is as below.

- Amine (Formula -1) and Oxirane (Formula-2) heated in methanol at 60°C for 20Hrs to get desired Intermediate-1. After completion of the reaction, reaction mass cooled and precipitated product was filtered, which on drying gives desired compound Intermediate-1.
- Above isolated (Intermediate-1) and CDI (1,1' carbonyl di imidazole) heated in Chlorobenzene at 100°C for 4Hrs to get desired Inter-2. After completion of the reaction, reaction mass cooled and precipitated product was filtered, which on drying gives desired compound Intermediate-2.

- Above isolated (Intermediate-2) treated with 40% aqueous MMA (Mono methyl amine) in ethanol at 60°C for 3Hrs to get desired Inter-3 free base, which on saltification with 65% nitric acid gives Nitrate salt of Intermediate-3.
- In the last step above isolated nitrate salt of Intermediate-3 coupled with Formula-5 in MDC and TEA at 35-40°C for 1Hr to get crude compound, which on further purification gives pure Rivaroxaban.

This process has certain drawbacks.

- As per this patent in each of the step (From ex 1, 2 and 3) after reaction time for each step is more, which in turn do not make the process viable for large scale manufacturing
- This prolonged period of reaction maintenance leads to an increase in the manufacturing cycle time and decrease in the product yield and quality

In the present work, we have incorporated micro flow reactor with telescoping process and with a single isolation only we got desired Rivaroxaban.

Over here Amine, Oxirane, CDI and Chloro thio compound were dissolve in a single solvent DMSO, MMA gas was already dissolved in DMSO and reaction ran sequentially through four different flow reactors to get desired crude compound, which on further purification gives pure Rivaroxaban.

Advantage of flow process over traditional batch process are less isolation, less reaction time, easy to do process, which can be easily implemented on large scale.

Over here we have used in-house fabricated micro reactors.

Solution preparation:

- Amine (Formula 1) was dissolved and diluted in DMSO to get 1.5M clear solution.
- Oxirane (Formula 2) was dissolved and diluted in DMSO to get 0.85M clear solution.
- CDI (1,1' carbonyl di imidazole) was dissolved and diluted in DMSO to get 2.2M clear solution (Formula 3)
- MMA (Mono methyl amine) gas was dissolved in DMSO in cooling condition at 0-5°C to get 2.5M clear solution (Formula 4)
- Chloro thio compound dissolved in DMSO to get 3M clear solution (Formula 5)

Flow reaction set-up:**[FIGURE-1]****FIGURE 1: FLOW REACTION SET-UP**

Amine (Formula 1) and oxirane (Formula 2) were combined in 10ml reactor (1st reactor) at 60°C with residence time **46 Seconds**, this intermediate (Intermediate-1) further combines with CDI (1,1' carbonyl di imidazole) in 10ml reactor (2nd reactor) at 60°C to form Oxazolidone as intermediate (Intermediate- 2) with residence time **36 Seconds**, Furthermore (Intermediate-2) combines with MMA solution in 20ml reactor (3rd reactor) at 60°C to form (Intermediate-3) with residence time **55 Seconds** which further combines with 3M Chloro thio compound (Formula -5) in 20ml reactor with residence time **43 Seconds** to give crude Rivaroxaban. This reaction moves through a back pressure regulator set to 0.5bar (Zaiput, BPR-10). At the output of BPR, samples were taken out and reaction progress was analyzed by TLC. After completion of the same, DM Water was added in reaction mass and desired product extracted by MDC. Separated MDC layer was charcolized at ambient temperature and distilled it completely U/Vacuum. Desired product was isolated by Acetone leaching. After drying at 50-55°C for 8-10Hrs, gives Rivaroxaban API.

[FIGURE – 2]**FIGURE – 2: MICRO-REACTOR**

Above experimented compound (Rivaroxaban) after isolation and drying, was analyzed by ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR. Data is attached with values.

^1H NMR:

White solid Rivaroxaban (5-chloro-N-((2-oxo-3-(4-(3-oxomorpholino)phenyl)oxazolidin-5-yl)methyl)thiophene-2-carboxamide) mp : 228-232°C

δ 3.594 - 3.622 (2H,t), J = 5.6Hz, δ 3.697 - 3.723 (2H,m), J = 5.2 Hz, δ 3.832 - 3.870 (2H,t), J = 6.4Hz, δ 3.956 - 3.981 (2H,t), J = 4.4Hz, 5.6Hz, δ 4.194 (2H,s), δ 4.809 - 4.874 (1H,m), 5.2Hz, 5.6Hz, δ 7.188 - 7.198 (1H,d), J = 4Hz, δ 7.393 - 7.416 (2H,dd) J = 2Hz, 4.8Hz, δ 7.547 - 7.570 (2H,dd), J = 2Hz, 6Hz, δ 7.684 - 7.695 (1H,d), J = 4Hz, δ 8.961 - 8.990 (1H,t), J = 5.8Hz

^{13}C NMR:

White solid Rivaroxaban (5-chloro-N-((2-oxo-3-(4-(3-oxomorpholino)phenyl)oxazolidin-5-yl)methyl)thiophene-2-carboxamide) mp : 228-232°C

δ 42.225 (1C, s), δ 47.433 (1C, s), δ 49.012 (1C, s), δ 63.481 (1C, s), δ 67.740 (1C, s), δ 71.353 (1C, s), δ 118.321 (2C, s), δ 125.950 (2C, s), δ 128.151 (1C, s), δ 128.447 (1C, s), δ 133.306 (1C, s), δ 136.494 (1C, s), δ 137.056 (1C, s), δ 138.468 (1C, s), δ 154.114 (1C, s), δ 160.828 (1C, s), δ 165.979 (1C, s)

Conclusion:

The prior sections have provided a clear picture of the significant and appealing advantages of flow process. That's why pharmaceutical companies are focusing on the utilization of flow chemistry in the production of APIs. This development is unstoppable and will only intensify in the future. The development of economically viable APIs provided an additional test platform for the established approach. A successful synthesis procedure for Rivaroxaban by constructing Oxazolidone heterocyclic ring was developed, and spectral analysis (^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR) was used to examine the finished product. By using micro flow reactor, the flow telescopic technique was used to synthesize it. This work is, to the best of our knowledge, the first instance of flow chemistry in a low-cost reactor. These developments in the flow system will eventually offer an affordable way to prepare medicinal compounds.

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REFERENCES -

1. Plutschack M.B, Pieber B and Gilmore K, The hitchhiker's guide to flow chemistry, *Chemical reviews*, 2017, vol 114, issue 18, pp 11796–11893, doi : 10.1021/acs.chemrev.7b00183
2. Gutmann B, Cappe O.C, Flow chemistry – continuous processing and continuous manufacturing : A pharmaceutical perspective, *Journal of flow chemistry*, 2017, vol 7, pp 137-145, doi : 10.1556/1846.2017.00029
3. Rodrigues T, Schneider P and Schneider G, Accessing new chemical entities through micro fluidic systems, *Angewandte chemie*, 2014, vol 53, issue 23, pp 5750-5758, doi : <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201400988>
4. Elvira K.S, Solvas X.C and Wootton R.C, The past, present and potential for micro fluidic reactor technology in chemical synthesis, *Nature chemistry*, vol 5, issue 11, pp 905-915, doi : 10.1038/nchem.1753
5. Roberge DM, Ducry L and Bieler N, Micro reactor technology: a revolution for the fine chemicals and pharmaceutical industries, *Micro reactor process design (special issue)*, 2005, vol 28, issue 3, pp 318 – 323, doi: 10.1002/ceat.200407128
6. Wiles C, Watts P, *Micro reaction technology in organic synthesis*, CRC Press, Boca Raton, 2011, eBook ISBN : 9780429093135,
7. T. Wirth, *Micro reactors in organic chemistry and atalysis*, second completely revised and enlarged edition, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2013
8. Phillippe HM, Overview of venous thromboembolism, *The American journal of managed care*,, 2017, vol 23, issue 20, pp 376 – 382,
9. Kasper DL, Braunwald E and Fauci AS, Thyroid function profile and its association to consumption of cassava and moringastenopetala in pregnant women, *McGraw-Hill*, 2005, vol 3 , issue 5, pp 1561 – 1565, doi : 10.4236/abc.2013.35048
10. Tohgi H, Konno S and Tamur K, Effects of low-to-high doses of aspirin on platelet agreeability and metabolites of thromboxane A2 and prostacyclin, 1992, *Stroke*, vol23, issue 10, pp 1400-1403, doi : 10.1161/01/str.23.10.1400

SUPPORTING INFORMATION:

Attached ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and D_2O exchange NMR with this

ABBREVIATIONS AND CONVENTIONS:

API	Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
μm	Micro meter
Mm	Mili meter
MW m^{-3} K-1	Mega watt meter cube per Kelvin
kW m^{-3} K-1	Kilo watt meter cube per Kelvin
$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Degree Celsius
Re	Reynolds number
PeL	The thermal Péclet number
DVT	Deep Vein Thrombosis
PE	Pulmonary Embolism
CDI	Carbonyldiimidazole
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
DMF	N,N-Dimethyl Form amide
DMAc	Dimethyl Acetamide
g	Gram
M	Molar
Sec	Seconds
MMA	Mono methyl amine
MMA-HCl	Mono methyl amine Hydrochloride
TLC	Thin Layer Chromatography
TMS	Tetra methyl silane
MHz	Mega Hertz
MDC	Methylene di chloride
TEA	Tri ethyl amine
BPR	Back pressure regulator
DM Water	De mineralized water
Hrs	Hours
Mp	Melting Point